

Long-term preservation solution as a Swiss national service

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Abstract

Within the framework of the DLCM (Data Life Cycle Management) project funded by the P5 program of swissuniversities, a long-term preservation system, called “OLOS” (see olos.swiss), has been developed for the archiving of research data. The DLCM project, which started in 2015, benefited from the data management expertise of eight Swiss project partner universities. OLOS is a platform that represents the first example of a generic FAIR repository at the national level, distinguished by its flexibility in deployment and its focus on long-term preservation. Its architecture adheres to the OAIS standard and consists of six main modules: (1) a pre-ingestion module responsible for preparing datasets for archiving, including metadata description, automatic format identification, virus checking, etc.; (2) the Submission Information Package (SIP) module for structuring the datasets and associating automatically generated administrative metadata with them; (3) the Archival Information Package (AIP) module, which complements the SIP to provide auditing and preservation of the datasets; (4) the Dissemination Information Package (DIP) module to provide access to the datasets, which, depending on the file formats, may offer advanced functionalities (e.g., 3D visualization); (5) the preservation policy module, which defines the number of replications, type of storage hardware, duration, migration policies, access rights, licensing, etc. and (6) the administrative module to monitor and manage the entire process. All these modules are independent and can be run separately in the cloud. For example, an institution may decide to have the AIP module and the preservation policy module on-site to maintain full control of the long-term archiving strategy, while relying on cloud servers for the other modules. In addition, to enable easy integration into the researchers’ work environment (e.g., Jupyter Notebook, LIMS, ELN, etc.), all modules can be addressed by a RESTful API or a Python-based client library. A user-friendly web interface is also provided so that researchers can interactively and collaboratively ingest datasets into a preservation space. However, scripts are provided to automate the bulk ingestion process. For each dataset, a unique and persistent identifier (DOI) is provided. Researchers are asked to supply minimal metadata to comply with the DataCite requirements. When additional research domain-specific metadata is provided, it will be part of the indexed information to facilitate reuse of the content by the research community. OLOS.swiss is a private non-profit organization created with the support of three founding members (UNIFR, HES-SO, HEG). The maintenance and development of the DLCM technology used by OLOS, is ensured by the UNIGE.

The DLCM project

The Swiss DLCM project^[1] was initially launched in September 2015 and gathered library and IT teams from eight Swiss higher education institutions (UNIZH, ETHZ, ZHAW, UNIBAS, EPFL, UNIL, UNIGE, HEG-Geneva, HES-SO). The first phase of the project focused

on the identification of the researchers' needs, which led to the documentation of main use cases and basic services, such as: access and contact point for information, training, and personalized advice, as well as active data management solutions, including long-term preservation, and data publication according to international standards^[2]. Two successive project phases concentrated on the design of a long-term data preservation solution for generic datasets, launched in December 2021. A multilingual national coordination desk offering tailored support, consulting and training to the academic community through a network of experts is another main outcome of the project.

The DLCM technology

Within this DLCM project framework, two implementations of long-term preservation systems (Yareta and OLOS) available through a Web portal have been realized in a perspective of safeguarding research and patrimonial information based on Swiss infrastructures. Yareta was first to be launched as a service limited to the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) of the Geneva area. Then, OLOS was made available at the national level, grounded in realistic business models to ensure financial sustainability^[3].

The main competitive advantage of the DLCM technology comes from its modular and distributed architecture, as well as its strict adherence to the OAIS (ISO 14721^[2]) reference model (Figure 1) and FAIR principles. The various modules of the solution offer a range of services that allow researchers to prepare their data for preservation. To the three standard OAIS entities (SIP, AIP, DIP), we have added a pre-ingestion module. This module allows for greater flexibility in data management by providing users with the ability to manipulate datasets prior to their final submission, including a DOI assignment to the datasets prior to the ingestion phase. The pre-ingestion comes after the phase of active work on the data, but before the archiving phase, which prevents any further modifications, with the exception of metadata. An intuitive user-centric portal allows for data submission and access, while hiding the complexity of OAIS mechanisms. In addition, all preservation services are available through web services (RESTful APIs), allowing, for instance, the integration of Jupyter Notebook with the DLCM technology.

The architecture is based on PREMIS^[4], METS^[5], and DataCite for the metadata, DOI for the persistent identifier, OAI-PMH for indexing and harvesting, and various connectors to different archive storage systems such as file system, S3, and tapes. For the next stage, we intend to add a new connector to store the information in DNA oligonucleotides^[6].

The organizational unit

A key concept of the DLCM technology is the organizational unit (OU) around which gravitates all the preservation activities (see Figure 2). For one, the OU defines who can access the datasets. It could be set at the level of a laboratory, a project, a department, or even a whole institution. The OU is linked not only to notifications concerning dataset ingestion but also to the pricing and billing of services.

Key features

The DLCM technology facilitates the process of capturing important information to describe a dataset, ensuring that access levels are appropriate based on the sensitivity of the data (see Figures 3 and 4). When depositing an archive, users must ask themselves the following questions :

1. To determine the appropriate “access level” for the archive and promote the openness of data to encourage open science practices, who should be granted access to the dataset ?
2. To ensure access to archives with sensitive data, what restriction scale (“Data Tag”) to apply ?
3. To determine the appropriate “License”, what terms and conditions should apply to the dataset’s use ?
4. To determine the “Data Use Agreement”, what obligations should be imposed on others who use the dataset ?

DLCM simplifies the process of making FAIR data available to users by encouraging citation with DataCite metadata and ensuring the "FAIRness" of data through a variety of means, including assigning archives a DOI for identification, using ORCID to identify researchers, ROR ID for institutions or funding agencies, and SPDX ID for licensing.

Another added value of DLCM is the compliance level. This concept is associated to each data file of a dataset. It allows to categorize each file with stars to automatically determine if the file format is suitable for long-term storage: ☆☆☆ unknown format; ★☆☆ identified format; ★★☆☆ identified format with PRONOM identifier of National archives of UK; ★★★ golden format based on recommended formats of Library of Congress.

Preservation planning

Another outcome that the DLCM project has yielded is a preservation planning module (preservation-centric workflows), that manages replication and synchronization of data stored across various data centers which use different technologies. This module represents a major capability that helps achieve the long-term preservation objectives. This notion defines the preservation strategy to be enforced by organizational units or by institution and sets the number of copies, geographic location, and physical multi-tiering support, such as spinning disks, tapes, and more. To expand technological options, we are currently considering DNA data storage.

Indeed, DNA data storage technology is progressing rapidly^[7], and a DNA-based solutions have many advantages:

- High density of information despite the redundancy needed to maintain the integrity of the information^[8];
- No energy needed to preserve the information packaged in substrates that ensure slow degradation^[9];
- No obsolescence (DNA is part of the building blocks of life).

However, a critical next step will be to integrate the experimental work into archival environments that provide self-describing encapsulation of the data and its metadata, long-term integrity and authenticity, and a study of the degradation of DNA libraries under real preservation conditions. The OAIS standard is well suited to cover these challenges and we are thus currently working on the development of a connector that will allow to preserve AIP in DNA.

From the DLCM technology to the OLOS service

DLCM technology can be applied on premise or as a cloud service. For the latter case, the DLCM project board has created OLOS (olos.swiss), an association open to any institution or individual. The founding members are three Swiss academic institutions. Three kinds of memberships are offered: gold, silver, and bronze. With the gold membership, the adherent has the option to synchronize one copy of each archive on their own infrastructure and the second on OLOS' data center. For this latter, data are guaranteed to be physically located on the Swiss territory. Fees for preserving data are based on data volume and preservation duration. Members of the association benefit from discounts on the pricing.

Being an open-source software, it is also possible to install on premise an instance of the DLCM technology from its source code repository (<https://gitlab.unige.ch/dlcm>). This option is currently being considered in Belgian academic institutions.

The educational and scientific dimensions are also developed in parallel. More than a solution, OLOS is a national service that includes various facilities for our academic partners. In addition to long-term preservation offers (different durations, volumes, etc.) it provides on-site and online trainings as well as ad hoc coaching activities for researchers from different Swiss HEIs, in English and French. These activities are carried out as part of an ongoing annual program and are delivered in partnership with DevPro (a Swiss training program) at the HES-SO in different locations in Switzerland. An advanced certification^[10] following an on-site exam, based on DLCM MOOC, has been created and is available since 2023 for Swiss and outsiders. The DLCM MOOC gives the possibility to obtain a certificate validated jointly by the HEG-GE, the DevPro training program of the HES-SO and OLOS.

An annual academic collaboration is set up to involve students from undergraduate and graduate programs in the study of various issues related to research data management. Recent thesis work has been published, e.g. on DNA archiving, Core Trust Seal certification processes and methods, etc.

In addition, regular events are organized to take part in key debates on challenging issues and trends in long-term storage and archiving. The Swiss Research Data Day^[11] is a meeting that brings together ideas, initiatives, and high-level national and international experts to discuss innovative ideas and emerging technologies. The scientific committee of OLOS^[12] supports the organization of this important event.

Conclusions

The significant work done on the basis of DLCM technology is intended to be shared openly and serves as a means of knowledge transfer. This success is taught in university courses in the field of information sciences. Our experiences are shared and disseminated through scientific and professional conferences, webinars, workshops and on-demand demonstrations.

The OLOS team is actively working on how to capitalize on the achievements already made and will continue to gain the trust of the academic partners. In this perspective, the maintenance of quality and the increase of performance will be ensured on the basis of the recently published policies and the various auditing processes. In this regard, the current CoreTrustSeal certification application can serve as an illustrative example.

OLOS invests in a broad vision for its future developments. An open, inclusive, and extensive collaboration network has been created in recent years with Swiss academic institutions and affiliated researchers as well as with international partners.

Sustainability, including its dual dimension - sustainable access to available data with low energy use - is more than central to the OLOS strategy. Our philosophy is to build on the network of experts and the national and international recognition to further invest in innovative and applied research in order to provide original and sustainable implementation models, methods and supporting tools to make research data processing and archiving more environmentally friendly. OLOS' current research has

progressed toward such achievements through its involvement in DNA Alliance. Recently, a PhD research project was launched in partnership with OLOS to develop and test a set of metrics, indicators and steering tools to better measure the ecological impacts of different storage and archiving methods and technologies.

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